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Peculiarities of traditional performance

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Abstract. *The history of the appearance of the first types of our musical heritage, the impact of musical instruments, traditional performance, kanda kashkar rubobi is discussed.*

Key words: *Music, culture, Musical instruments, Risolayi music, musical heritage, traditional performance.*

СТУДЕНТ ФАКУЛЬТЕТА ИСКУССТВ КАРАКАЛПАКСКОГО
ГОСУДАРСТВЕННОГО УНИВЕРСИТЕТА ИМЕНИ БЕРДАКА

Аннотация. *Обсуждается история появления первых видов нашего музыкального наследия, влияние музыкальных инструментов, традиционного исполнительства, канда кашкар рубоби.*

Ключевые слова: *музыка, культура, музыкальные инструменты, рисолайская музыка, музыкальное наследие, традиционное исполнительство.*

The appearance of the first types of our musical heritage corresponds to the works before our era. According to historical sources, in the Middle Ages, percussion, bell, and percussion instruments were widely used. According to the sources, rubob-like tools were also widespread among the Movaronahir peoples in the 2nd-3rd centuries AD.

Unfortunately, there are very few sources that provide information about the musical culture of the peoples of Central Asia before Islam. Rubob sozi, which belongs to the dynasty of percussion sounds, is one of the decorative sounds of the musical life of the Uzbek people. We can find information about Rubab in pamphlets written in the 10th-17th centuries. According to the sources, it is indicated in some sources that there was rubob soz in Movaronahir. It is angular in shape and is counted from the bow strings.

The musical instruments had a single cord. The musical parts of the musical parts of the stories and the narrators, the narrators of the stories, which they protect, are performed through this music. It is worth noting that in our time, as in most Arab countries, narrators also use the word "Reboba" widely in their performances. Here are a few words about the narrators: Narrators mean the one who narrates, they used the tunes of different peoples in order to increase the effectiveness of the reality they narrate.

The narrators are similar to our Bakhshis with their qualities. It is known from history that in the 12th and 13th centuries there was also a rubob song among bowed songs. In the 12th century, this phrase was loved by all the Mawlawi peoples. According to the creed of Maulavis representatives, each corner of the word rubab has a certain symbolic meaning, according to the creed of Maulavis the first corner is east, the second corner is west, the third corner is south, and the fourth corner is north. means 'names'. Later, they remade this tune in the shape of a hexagon. In this case, the 5th corner means the earth's surface and the 6th corner means the sky. Undoubtedly, these corners have mystical meanings.

In terms of the structure of this verse, it is somewhat similar to the Dynasty of Rubabs. The Kashgar rubobi began to appear in ensembles around the 14th-15th centuries. The initial

appearance of Rubab was smaller than the current one. The curtains are connected with a special device made of intestines and are clicked with a soft object. By the 19th century, the rubob was greatly improved, its strings were increased to 4 and curtains to 18. Various historical and political events that took place at the end of the 19th century and the beginning of the 20th century due to changes, a number of innovations began to appear in our traditional performance. Until the 20s of the 20th century, the influence of various traditional performers on the development of Uzbek music is increasing. In 1917-1950, Russian music again influenced the development of Uzbek music. This effect, in turn, forms the basis of academic performance in the music and voice.

In the 1930s and 1940s, the master musician Muhammadjon Mirzaev used matap strings instead of silk strings on the rubob instrument. In the 1950s, metal parts glued to the curtain rod took the place of the curtains. In the book "History of Uzbek Classical Music" by Adurauf Fitrat, a famous literary scholar and scholar of our music, the following is written about rubab: in an "musical history" whose author is unknown, it is written that rubab appeared in Khorezm by Sultan Mohammad Khorazimshah. The day I saw this book, I relied on it.

However, I was surprised by the resemblance of a sorang instrument brought from India in the twenties. Later, Darvish Ali's "Risalai muziyy" of this instrument, which came into my hands, shows that this instrument was made in Balkh and flourished in Khorazim during the time of Mohammad Khorazimshah. The body of this instrument can be divided into four main parts. Abdomen, chest, neck, head, abdomen, and chest are made from one piece of mulberry wood by "Kozma" method. The head part is then made and glued to the stem.

Kashgar rubobi has a special place in Uzbek music. This musical instrument has become one of the favorite musical instruments of our people due to its sonority and closeness to the human heart, as well as the ease of learning and playing. Skilled musicians such as Muhammadjon Mirzaev, Ergash Shukrulaev, Abbas Bahromov, Ari Bobokhanov, Suleiman Pakhalov, Qabil Usmanov, Adham Khudoykulov, Takhir Rajabov, Rifatulla Kasimov make a great contribution to the popularity and popularity of kashkar rubo among our people.

The famous musicians of the above-mentioned kashgar rubabi created a unique performance school in the republic. At the same time, they made a great effort in the training of musicians and pedagogues in this specialty in the countries of the Central Asian republics.

In fact, today, Kashkar rubobi is considered one of the most capable of performing not only traditional music, but also musical works created by all nations of the world, as well as composers. Darveshali Chang's "Risalai Musiky", Abdurauf Fitrat's "Songs of Uzbek Classical Music", F Karomatov's "Uzbek Instrumental Music" by T.S. "Central Asian musical instruments" by Vizgon, A. Exgor's "Musical ethnographic materials", G. Pugachenkova, L. Rempel's "Essay on Central Asian Art", I. Petrosiya's scientific monographs, such as "Cholghunoslik", contain important information about the songs of the Uzbek folk instruments as well as the Kashgar rubobi. As a matter of fact, the information, definition and descriptions of rubob sozi are given by the great thinkers of Central Asia A. Firdavsi, A. Rudakiy, A. Bedil, A. It can be found in the works of Navoi and Babur.

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